

Uses of *Rauwolfia serpentina* in the case of Hypertension

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DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17346132

J. Evid. Based Homeopath.2025:3(1):7-11.

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Abstract

In many cases of hypertension, patients taking allopathic antihypertensive drugs still fail to achieve proper blood pressure control. At my clinic, while treating patients for other health issues, I observed that their blood pressure often remained uncontrolled despite using these agents. To address this, I prescribed *Rauwolfia serpentina* in homoeopathic form along with their existing allopathic medicines. In several cases, this combination controlled hypertension effectively and even helped avoid increasing the dose of allopathic drugs. In 2019, I studied 5 such patients with uncontrolled hypertension. After proper case recording and prescription of their indicated homoeopathic remedy, *Rauwolfia serpentina* was given as an additional antihypertensive agent. Their blood pressure gradually reduced and normalized. Later, in 2022, I successfully treated more than 1000 patients with similar results, though those cases are not included in this study. This observation highlights the efficacy of homoeopathic *Rauwolfia serpentina* in controlling blood pressure in patients already on allopathic antihypertensive medication.

Keywords: Uncontrolled hypertension, hypertension, allopathic antihypertensive agent, homoeopathic *Rauwolfia serpentina*.

Introduction

Hypertension is the term used to describe high blood pressure. Blood pressure is the measurement of the force against the walls of arteries as the heart pumps blood through the body. Conventionally blood pressure readings are measured in millimeters of mercury (mmHg) as systolic pressure and diastolic pressure. Systolic pressure is considered high if it is over 140 most of the time, where as diastolic pressure is considered high if it is over 90 most of the time. Prevalence of hypertension increases with age.¹

Hypertension is a major risk factor for stroke and MI. It is usually asymptomatic, and regular screening (eg- 3 yearly) is a vital primary care task. It causes-50% of all vascular deaths (8 x 10⁶ per year). Most preventable deaths are in areas without universal screening.¹

Defining hypertension- Blood pressure has a skewed normal distribution within the population, and risk is continuously related to blood pressure, so it is impossible to define hypertension. Assess BP over a period of time (don't rely on a single reading). The observation period depends on the BP and the presence of other risk factors.¹

Whom to treat- All with BP > 160/100 mmHg. For those > 140/90 mmHg the decision depends on the risk of coronary events, presence of diabetes or end organ damage (table-1).¹

Types of HTN: There are three main categories of hypertension,¹

1. **Malignant HTN:** This refers to severe hypertension (eg >200 /

>130 mmHg). B/L retinal hemorrhages and exudates; papilledema may or may not be present. Symptoms are common eg- headache, visual disturbance.

2. **Essential HTN:** Primary causes are unknown, 95% of all cases.
3. **Secondary HTN:** 5 % of all cases. Causes are – Renal disease, Endocrinal diseases, etc.¹

Table-1: Defining hypertension¹

Category	Systolic mmHg	Diastolic mmHg
Optimal BP	< 120	<75
Normal BP	121-129	76-84
High Normal BP	130 - 139	85 -89
Mild HTN	140 – 159	90 – 99
Moderate HTN	160 – 179	100 – 109
Severe HTN	>_ 180	>_110

Diagnostic evaluation

When the patient with HTN, come to my clinic I checked their BP for contiguous 2 visits, if their BP is high for contiguous 2 visits after taken allopathy antihypertensive agent then, I have prescribe *Rauwolfia serpentina* to them and check BP for next 2 visits and this data have saved. (Both arm BP have been checked at a time and save data).

Process of examination

1. The BP instrument should be placed at a leveled surface at about the level of heart.
2. Scale of the instrument should be at the level of the

observer's eyes.

3. Patient should be at maximum mental and physical rest and sufficient time is to be allowed to recover from any recent exercise or emotional upset for which at least half an hour rest given.
4. Blood pressure is measured either in sitting or lying down positions.

Method of noting BP in my study

1. Palpatory method
2. Auscultatory method

Dosage: *Rauwolfia serpentina* mother tincture 15 drops in 1/2 cup of water thrice a day after meal and some cases I have used Rauwolfia serpentina 1X tablets, 2 tablets twice in a day after meal.

Laboratory Investigations

For rare cases I have done, below investigations.

1. **CXR** - PA view- To confirm any cardiomegaly, or pulmonary edema.
2. **ECG** - To confirm any MI, LVH, Arrhythmia, Ischemia, etc.
3. **ECHO** - To confirm LVH, EF, Valvular pathology
4. **Blood for Na** - In that case, where the patient have taken anti-HTN agents drug
5. **Blood for creatinine** - In that case where the patient have Amlodipine like antihypertensive drug
6. **Blood for Lipid profile**

About Homoeopathic medicine *Rauwolfia serpentina*

Rauwolfia serpentina is one of the most often used homoeopathic drugs for hypertension. It belongs to the family Apocynaceae and is found in sub-Himalayan ranges and Western Ghats of India.⁷ It is officially covered by both Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia of India and German Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia.^{8,9} The root contains a great number of alkaloids of which Reserpine is the most well known. Its hypotensive and neuro-depressive activities are established.² A homoeopathic tincture is made from its root. Literatures and *Rauwolfia serpentina* in homeopathy indicate that this remedy is useful to manage high blood pressure. It also alleviates its associated symptoms such as irregular beats, increased emotional excitability, irritative condition of central nervous system, mild depression, irritability and restlessness. Reports suggest it is highly useful in cases of hypertension without marked atheromatous changes in the vessels.^{2,3,4,5,6}

MASTER CHART

Case No.	Before study BP	After use Rauwolfia	Only on Rauwolfia	Stop Rauwolfia	Use both	Visit Next	Visit Next
1	S-140 D-100	S-110 D-80	S-130 D-98	S-140 D-90	S-140 D-90	S-130 D-90	S-120 D-80
2	S-140 D-98	S-120 D-90	S-130 D-96	S-120 D-100	S-130 D-90	S-138 D-90	S-120 D-90
3	S-160 D-110	S-140 D-96	Not check	S-160 D-100	S-120 D-90	S-130 D-88	S-120 D-90
4	S-170 D-120	S-150 D-110	S-160 D-110	S-150 D-110	S-150 D-98	S-150 D-98	S-160 D-110
5	S-160 D-106	S-130 D-96	S-120 D-94	Not check	S-140 D-90	S-130 D-90	S-120 D-80

N.B: There are so many cases are there only 5 of them are taken.

CHART PRESENTATION

Discussion

From this study outcome, it have been seen that Homoeopathic *Rauwolfia serpentina* is very much effective for the case of HTN, specially on that case where patient have hypertension and taken allopathic antihypertensive agent but no control over their HTN. Some time it also have been seen that, only Homoeopathic *Rauwolfia serpentina* may sufficient, after tapered off the allopathic antihypertensive agent at the known case of hypertension.

My aim is to know the action or reproving the specific homoeopathic medicine on a specific condition like hypertension.

Abbreviation

HTN	Hypertension
CXR	Chest Xray
PA	Posterior to Anterior
ECG	Electrocardiogram
ECHO	Echocardiogram
Na	Sodium
eg	Example
BP	Blood Pressure
MI	Myocardial infarction
LVH	left ventricular hypertrophy

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